

extent, after the root-dip treatment, appears to have more practical significance. In most treatments the number of infections was reduced, but in some, lesion expansion was also inhibited

Sporulation in *Drechslera oryzae*

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Brown leaf spot of rice caused by *Drechslera oryzae* is an important disease of rice in Karnataka, India. The pathogen causes small spots or lesions on the leaves. The isolated spots are oblong or oval, dark brown, and scattered along the leaf. *D. oryzae* does not sporulate on infected green leaves or senescent leaves. But when such leaves were detached and the water-soluble components leached out, then sporulation was abundant. Infected leaves are not the inoculum source for glume infection in Karnataka, as the pathogen does not sporulate on the leaves. Hence, a water-soluble component of the leaf spot was presumed to inhibit sporulation. Therefore, the effect of leaching this component with water was tested.

The cut ends of rice leaves were immersed in distilled water in a flask for 48 hours at room temperature and at 30, 35, 40, and 45°C. Water in the flask was changed at six hourly intervals. The leaves were then removed and kept in a moist chamber. Abundant sporulation from the leaf spots was evident within 48 hours, but the pathogen was killed at 45°C. That indicates that the leaf spots may contain a water-soluble component that inhibits sporulation. ■

Effect of carbon sources on sporulation of *Drechslera oryzae*

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The effect of arabinose, carboxy-cellulose, fructose, galactose, glucose, mannose, rhamnose, ribose, starch, sucrose, and

xylose on sporulation was tested from 0.5 to 9.0% levels by replacing sucrose in Richard's medium. Sporulation was observed in the media containing mannose, starch, and sucrose. The fungus showed limited sporulation in the media with sucrose at 2.5% level. Sporulation was completely suppressed at 3.5%. Maximum sporulation was obtained with mannose at 2.5% concentration and with starch at 6.5%. ■

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Antagonistic action of soil microbes on *Drechslera oryzae*

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Trichoderma sp. isolated from semidry and puddled soils parasitized *Drechslera oryzae* (Breda de Haan) Subram and Jain, whereas *Streptomyces* sp. isolated from the two soils showed inhibitory action on *D. oryzae*, *Bacillus* sp.—present in puddled soil, but not in semidry soil — showed inhibitory action when inoculated on *D. oryzae* on petri plates.

Survival of *Drechslera oryzae* in an aerobic condition

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An experiment on the growth and survival of *Drechslera oryzae* was conducted with the following treatments.

1. Slants with agar medium plugged with cotton dipped in pyrogallol acid + 1 N NaOH (to create complete anaerobic conditions).
2. Mouth of the test tube covered with paraffin (to create partial anaerobic conditions).
3. Control (without above treatments).

The pathogen did not grow in the first treatment and was killed in less than 7 days. When the mouth of the test tube was covered with paraffin, there was growth and the pathogen survived for 4 weeks. But in the control treatment, growth was excellent and *D. oryzae* survived for 18 weeks. This experiment was conducted to verify whether *D. oryzae* can survive in completely or partially anaerobic conditions, as those that prevail in puddled soils. According to these results it can be assumed that *D. oryzae* may not survive for a long time in paddy soil and the fungus in the soil may not serve as a source of inoculum. ■

A soft rot disease of rice observed at IRRI

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In 1978, a soft rot disease was observed on plants of IR129-192-2 in the International Rice Yield Nursery grown at IRRI. Infection was evident from the early to the maximum tillering stages. The infected plants' leaf sheaths and tissues from the basal internodes showed browning and water soaking, accompanied by rotting and a foul odor. The symptoms suggested that bacteria caused the infection, which was similar to an infection observed on IR36 in 1977.

Infected tissues were isolated on potato sucrose agar and incubated at 30°C for 48 hours. Two distinct colony types, Type A and Type B, were apparent on the agar plates. Type A colony was milky white and flat with irregular margins. Type B colony was creamy yellow and slightly raised with irregular margins. On peptone sucrose agar plates, Type B was creamy white to very light yellow. Its surface was slightly raised and rough; the margin was irregular. In addition, a brown pigment diffused to the medium 3 days after incubation. Both colony types produced gas on Wakimoto's medium, produced fluorescent pigment on the same medium under ultraviolet light, and caused potato slices to rot.

A pathogenicity test with 24-hour

cultures was made on a detached stem. Inoculated tissues were discolored from light to dark brown. Four days after pot-grown plants of IR8 were inoculated at the maximum tillering stage, symptoms began to appear. A lesion extended upward and downward from the inoculation point; the leaf sheath became

brown. But the lesion was restricted only to the inoculated internodes in which the stem tissues as well as the leaf sheath became rotten and discolored. The outer leaves of infected plants senesced rapidly.

Initial bacteriological studies indicated that the causal bacterium may be similar to that which causes "bacterium bruzone

disease" of rice in Hungary or "sheath brown rot" of rice in Japan. According to Goto, the pathogen was closely related to *Pseudomonas marginalis*, but different from the "sheath rot" caused by a strain of *Erwinia carotovora* in Indonesia in 1964. The etiology and identification of the bacterium are being studied. ■

Occurrence of rice ragged stunt disease in West Bengal, India

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In the 1978 wet season, natural infection of rice ragged stunt disease was observed

on Jaya in a trial plot of the Rice Production Training Institute farm. About 50% of the rice hills were affected. The population of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* was low at the time. Scattered diseased plants were later found in isolated pockets in the region. This is the first report of ragged stunt in

West Bengal. The primary symptoms of the disease observed were stunting (photo 1), vein-swelling on ragged leaves (photo 2), distorted twisting of the flag leaf, and incomplete emergence of the panicle (photo 3).

1. Healthy plant (right) and stunted plant (left) infected with ragged stunt disease.

2. Vein-swelling on ragged leaves.

3. Incomplete emergence of panicle and twisted flag leaf.

Serological studies of rice ragged stunt virus

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Crude or partially purified material containing B-spiked subviral particles (SVP) of rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV) from diseased plants (mailed to Italy from the Philippines) was injected into rabbits for antiserum production. When tested by the gel diffusion method, the antiserum had a titer of 1/16 against healthy rice material, and at least 1/64 against RRSV preparations. When the antiserum was tested by immunoelectron microscopy using the decoration technique, specific antibody halos around

SVP of RRSV were detected up to a dilution of 1/256. Preparations of SVP of maize rough dwarf virus (MRDV), oat sterile dwarf virus (OSDV), and pangola stunt virus (PSV) were not decorated by the RRSV antiserum. Likewise, the antisera of MRDV, OSDV, PSV, and sugarcane Fiji disease virus failed to decorate SVP of RRSV. Thus, RRSV is not serologically related to those viruses that make up the fijiviruses group, but might be a new member of a plant reovirus group having affinities with the fijiviruses. Furthermore, the antiserum reacted positively to diseased materials collected in India, Indonesia, Philippines, and Thailand. Hence, in addition to being similar in symptomatology and transmission, the RRSV in those countries are serologically related.

Effect of nitrogen on lesion development in rice resistant to bacterial blight

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It is generally believed that increases in nitrogen fertilizer increase bacterial blight infection. If rices with different resistance genes and pathotypes with specific virulence are identified, then scientists can evaluate interactions among nitrogen fertilizer and those factors. Initial greenhouse experiments showed that the lesion length on varieties with intermediate (moderate or partial) resistance, such as Pulo and Sailboro 302, increased with increased nitrogen level. But the total lesion length was considerably less than that on rices with